

EVALUATION ON END-OF-COURSE SPEAKING TESTS IN HUFLIT

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ABSTRACT

During a period of over 20 years, Role-play _ a popular style in Interactive Approach used especially for teaching_ has been mainly applied for all speaking tests in all departments of HUFLIT (Ho Chi Minh University of Foreign Languages & Information Technology) for its advantages: time-saving, simple and easy for both testers and testees. However, the results seem not tally with expectations when negative feedbacks from both lecturers and employers_ the crucial element in the update tertiary educational reform_ rush in.

The study is partially withdrawn from the hands-on experience of the writer with a hope to produce an analysis on the procedures and techniques of the test design, particularly in oral tests applied for the courses ranging from Speaking 1, Speaking 2, Speaking 3, Speaking 4. The principle is that the test-takers have a great deal to offer to the test researchers in making judgments about the value of the tests which they take (Brown, 1994).

The paper mainly investigates some issues circling the use of the popular speaking test tasks, especially referring to group discussion and Role-play, in HUFLIT's Department of Foreign Languages based on the test criteria proposed by well-known researchers in the world and have been widely applied in the tests such as IELTS, TOEFL, TOEIC, Cambridge, Michigan..., through data from informal interviews, questionnaires and aims to find out shortcomings leading to unexpected outcomes and also provide some recommendations that can be helpful in building up closer-to-the-norm tests with better results.

Keywords: Role-play, Interactive Approach, end-of-course speaking tests, oral tests, HUFLIT, test criteria, IELTS, TOEFL, TOEIC, Cambridge, Michigan, closer-to-the-norm tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

The new strategy of the educational institutions is to link classroom knowledge and skills to the job markets, expecting a breakthrough in the education reform, an improvement in unemployment ratio, a recognition from the Ministry of Education and Training, and a better status in their business competition.

With the international and regional integration, the job market is forecast very competitive and the Vietnamese job-seekers may dramatically suffer from their poorly trained working skills and

English. One of the HUFLIT's missions is to produce graduates, well equipped with not only good ability in their expertise, but also real competence in computer and foreign language(s). The renovation in all aspects has been widely worked out in which improving students' English speaking skill is viewed a priority.

A few years ago, in a HUFLIT's Science council annual meeting, the then Head of IT department repeated the employers' comments on the new graduates that they are "good at IT but poor at English speaking". Some lecturers in the Department of Foreign languages also felt frustrated when part of students could not perform adequate speaking skill in the classroom. A series of solutions were made up since then, such as: adding 1 more subject known as Public Speaking 2; opening the English-speaking club; using native teachers in the classroom. However, these solutions did not bring about good results as expected: the club could not attract participants and some native teachers were not well-trained.

1.2 Statement of the problem

HUFLIT' traditional English oral test task has not been much updated for over 2 decades with the various forms ranging from face-to-face interview to role-play: Role-play, a distinctive feature from the Interactive Approach in ELT around the end of the previous century, is a good choice for teaching and learning rather than for testing. While the specific objective of the Foreign language (hereby referred to as English) department curriculum is producing graduates being able to communicate, negotiate with native speakers in almost all common fields, in unprofessional level, ranging from: medical science, economy, finance, foreign affairs, education, business of all sorts, society, world updates, science, etc., Role-play task in the final tests of all levels, usually pair work, just requests examinees to communicate with each other in some familiarly learned topics with a well preparation in descriptions, situations, transitional sentences, and so on. The test takers always tend to provide simple questions that his partner(s) can fluently answer.

As a result, oral test takers can easily pass the tests owing to much simpler level compared to a conversation with English native speakers (less complex in terms of knowledge, vocabulary, structure). They also automatically lose their motivation in upgrading their speaking skill leading to failures of the English Speaking Club and other efforts. In addition, the single task of Role-play in the test cannot assess other aspects as Oral Proficiency Interview (OPI) tests do.

With the writer's long hands-on experience as a tester of the oral language tests, some visible shortcomings of the traditional English speaking test task have been identified and suggestions will be provided with a hope the problem can soon be solved.

1.3 Hypothesis

Test takers' motivation and real competence can be improved if the end-of-course English oral test tasks in HUFLIT are changed towards those in international tests such as TOEFL, IELTS or TOEIC.

1.4 Research questions

The research question in this minor study circles around the view of students on the English oral tests that all of them experienced:

What are the shortcomings of the traditional English oral tests in HUFLIT?

What can be the better replacement for HUFLIT's case? Comparison?

1.5 Significance of the study

The purpose of my study is to identify the drawbacks of the traditional end-of-course English oral tests in HUFLIT for modifications to upgrade the testing system, to help improve students' motivation and real competence to cope with international tests, a requirement in the job market, also one of the biggest flaws for Vietnamese job seekers, and to meet the innovation demand from the institution.

1.6 Scope and delimitation of the study

The study can be popularly employed in VN's other institutions including those of still apply various forms of the oral test. However, an apparent setback of my proposal is that not all universities are eager for the change that may be costly, time and effort consuming in the status of lacking adequate professionals.

This is just a pilot study with a small number of participants; therefore, its conclusions may be not true when it is repeated on a larger scale.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Farzana Naheed (2010) a loyal supporter of Interactive Approach advised that the approach be frequently applied in teaching English as a foreign language classroom. He never said it can be used as a replacement for any oral test worldwide. It can be simply understood that not all teaching activities can be automatically employed in testing.

The popular formula in teaching and testing from Stodolla (1995) "Test what we teach" does not mean the test designs or techniques. What it referred to is knowledge.

The ACTFL Provisional Proficiency Guidelines, published in 1982, divided proficiency: "...level 0 was renamed Novice and subdivided into Novice Low, Novice Mid, and Novice High, while level 1 was renamed Intermediate and subdivided into Intermediate Low, Intermediate Mid, and Intermediate High. Level 2 was renamed Advanced, and levels 3, 4, and 5 on the Government scale were combined into a single level called Superior, because data had shown that few university graduates reach even level 3" (ERIC Custom Transformations Team 1992). That HUFLIT divides English speaking proficiency into 4 categories is to go with the characteristics of the academic year system that have long been existed before the credit system. It is also similar to the curricula of most Vietnamese language departments.

Marysia Johnson (2000) cited ETS (1989) that "a well structured OPI tests speaking ability in a real life context - conversation" and strongly argued that "The OPI does not test speaking ability

in a real life context - conversation. It tests speaking ability in the context of an interview, or more precisely, in the context of a survey research interview, ..." (pp. 215).

In her study, Marysia Johnson (2000) also confirmed that: "The Oral Proficiency Interview (OPI) is a widely used instrument for assessing second and foreign language speaking ability within government institutions such as the Foreign Service Institute (FSI) and Defense Language Institute (DLI), and nongovernment institutions such as the Educational Testing Service (ETS) and the American Council on the Teaching of Foreign Languages (ACTFL) (p. 216). She described the test: "In the OPI, which is based on the ACTFL/ETS/ILR scale and speaking level descriptions, the examinee converses face to face with one or two trained testers on a variety of topics for 10 to 30 minutes...(p. 216). She also gave a remark on the popularity of the test worldwide: "It is estimated that several thousand OPI tests are administered each year. Frequently, entire professional careers, future job assignments, pay-increases, and entrance or exit from college language programs depend on the rating obtained during the oral interview (p. 216).

Another form of the speaking test is known as simulated oral proficiency interview (SOPI), which is a type of semi-direct speaking test that models, as closely as is practical, the format of the oral proficiency interview (OPI)(ERIC Custom Transformations Team1989). It is described as a tape-recorded test consisting of six parts. "It begins with simple personal background questions posed on the tape in a simulated initial encounter with a native speaker of the target language. These parts assess the examinee's ability to handle the functions and content that characterize the Advanced and Superior levels of the ACTFL guidelines, or levels two through four of the ILR skill level descriptions. Like the OPI, the SOPI ends with a "wind-down." This is usually an easy question designed to put the examinee at ease and to facilitate the ending of the examination in as natural a manner as possible"(ERIC Custom Transformations Team1989).

3 METHODS OF STUDY AND SOURCES OF DATA

3.1 Research Purpose

Realizing poor command of spoken English in some students; the failure of the supporting efforts such as: English speaking club, learning groups, ...; students' loss of motivation in learning speaking; negative feedback from enterprises, the writer conducts the study with the aims to improve learners' proficiency in spoken English to cope with international tests, to enhance their motivation, to help them gain and upgrade their real competence for fierce competitions in the job market.

3.2 Population of the Study

All of the respondents are students in the Research Methodology and Translation-Interpretation classrooms in HUFLIT. The number of respondents is rather humble, 42, not satisfactory for a research but this can be seen a pilot study in HUFLIT for further researches. All are in the range of 21-22, except for two of over 24. They all were already experienced and passed speaking end-of-course tests of 4 levels. This is the rationale for the writer's choice hoping they can effectively

contribute their knowledge to the study to help improve the traditional 25-year-old oral testing system in HUFLIT.

3.3 Instrument Used

With the humble scope of the article, the only tool in the study is data collection from attitude questionnaires distributed June 15 and collected July8. The questionnaires were sent to participants by posting in Facebook groups to assure the prompt reception and 42 were returned via email before the deadline for the convenience of data collection.

3.4 Statistical Treatment

Statistical data is treated with SPSS to show the percentage of agreement/disagreement and the individual solutions/proposals/personal views from the participants.

4 PRESENTATION, DATA ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Presentation and Data analysis

Q 1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
A	4	9.5	9.5	9.5
B	19	45.2	45.2	54.8
C	10	23.8	23.8	78.6
D	9	21.4	21.4	100.0
Valid				
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Question 1 (Q1) is about students' proficiency after Speaking 4. Only 21.4% (9 participants) were confident to agree that they can communicate with the native speaker of the target language with all topics (business, economy, finance, defense, world updates) and with unprofessional level. 54.7% (23) did not think they can. Especially, 23.8% (10) were not sure about their proficiency.

Q2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
A	6	14.3	14.3	14.3
B	8	19.0	19.0	33.3
C	2	4.8	33.3	66.6
D	12	28.6	28.6	95.2
E	14	33.3	33.3	100.0
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Q2 asks if test takers feel at ease with Role play. 23.8 (10) agreed. 33.3% were not sure. 42.9% (14) did not accept it.

Q3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
A	6	14.3	14.3	14.3
B	2	4.8	4.8	19.0
C	2	4.8	4.8	23.8
D	15	35.7	35.7	59.5
E	17	40.5	40.5	100.0
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Q3 checks if Role play provides test topics beforehand. 86.2% (32) agreed. 4.8% (2) had no idea. 19.1% (8) disagreed.

Q4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
A	8	19.0	19.0	19.0
B	4	9.5	9.5	28.5
C	11	26.2	26.2	54.7
D	14	33.3	33.3	88.1
E	5	11.9	11.9	100.0
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Q4 checks if Role play gives examinees time for preparation and memorizing the questions for their partners. The majority 76.2% (32) agreed. 19.2% (8) said no and only 4.8% (2) had no idea.

Q5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
B	6	14.3	14.3	14.3
C	8	19.0	19.0	33.3
Valid D	13	31.0	31.0	64.3
E	15	35.7	35.7	100.0
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Q5 checks if Role play allows test takers to learn transitional sentences. 45.5% (19) said that is true. 28.5% (12) did not agree. Up to 26.2% (11) were not sure.

Q6

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid A	2	4.8	4.8	4.8
B	9	21.4	21.4	26.2
C	2	4.8	4.8	31.0
D	6	14.3	14.3	45.2
E	23	54.8	54.8	100.0
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Q6 asks how easy speaking test in HUFLIT is with well preparation for in reality, the passing rate is very high. 66.7% (28) accepted it is. 14.3% (6) did not think so. 19% (8) had no opinion.

Q7

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
A	2	4.8	4.8	4.8
B	9	21.4	21.4	26.2
Valid C	14	33.3	33.3	59.5
D	10	23.8	23.8	83.3
E	7	16.7	16.7	100.0
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Q7 asks if communication with Vietnamese partners in the test is easier than that with native speakers. 40.5% (17) accepted. 26.2% (11) disagreed. 33.3% (14) were not sure.

Q8

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
A	2	4.8	4.8	4.8
B	8	19.0	19.0	23.0
C	5	11.9	11.9	44.9
D	16	38.1	38.1	82.9
E	11	26.2	26.2	100.0
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Q8 is about whether understanding and answering the native speakers is challenging. 64.3% (27) agreed. 23.8% (10) disagreed. 11.9% (5) had no opinion.

Q9

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
A	8	19.0	19.0	19.0
B	8	19.0	19.0	38.1
C	17	40.5	40.5	78.6
D	4	9.5	9.5	88.1
E	5	11.9	11.9	100.0
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Q9 checks students' knowledge about if international oral tests are identical to HUFLIT oral test. 21.4% (9) said they are. 38% (16) said they are not. Up to 40.5% (17) had no opinion.

Q10

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
A	2	4.8	4.8	4.8
B	11	26.2	26.2	31.0
C	7	16.7	16.7	47.6
D	6	14.3	14.3	61.9
E	16	38.1	38.1	100.0
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Q10 asks if the difficulty of TOEFL, IELTS, TOEIC oral tests is higher than that of HUFLIT oral test. 62.4% (22) agreed. 31% (13) disagreed. 16.7 (7) were not sure

Q11

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
A	6	14.3	14.3	14.3
C	12	28.6	28.6	42.9
Valid D	16	38.1	38.1	81.0
E	8	19.0	19.0	100.0
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Q11 asks if the TOEFL, IELTS, TOEIC oral tests aim at varied tested targets than Role play does. 37.1 (24) accepted. 14.3 (6) did not. 28.6 (12) had no opinion.

Q12

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
B	15	35.7	35.7	35.7
C	9	21.4	21.4	57.1
Valid D	14	33.3	33.3	90.5
E	4	9.5	9.5	100.0
Total	42	100.0	100.0	

Q12 is most important. It asks if Role play should be changed for a closer-to-the-norm test. 42.8% (18) said yes. 35.7 (15) said no. 21.4 (9) had no opinion.

4.2 Discussion

The following test structures are to clear-cut the differences of international tests and HUFLIT's test that its shortcomings can be identified as the research question poses.

4.2.1 Structure of the oral proficiency interview

Johnson (2000) briefed the structure of OPI: "The OPI has both a general and a level-specific structure. The OPI consists of four phases: Warm-up, Level Checks, Probes, and Wind-Down. The purpose of the Warm-up phase is to give the testers a preliminary indication of the candidate's level of speaking proficiency. The purpose of the Level Check is to find out the candidate's highest sustainable level of speaking proficiency. When the candidate successfully passes the Level Check, his/her performance provides a floor for the rating. The purpose of the Probes phase is to show the tester(s) whether the candidate has reached his/her highest level of speaking proficiency. The last phase is the Wind-Down. The purpose of this phase is to leave the candidate with a feeling of accomplishment" (Johnson 2000:217).

4.2.2 TOEFL question type

“The Speaking section has 6 tasks. There are 3 formats used. The first format gives 15 seconds to prepare and 45 seconds to speak. The first question will be about a familiar topic that you answer based on personal experience. The second question will also be about a familiar topic that you answer by giving your opinion. The second format gives 30 seconds to prepare and 60 seconds to speak. For each of the 2 questions you read a short passage and then will hear and watch (like in Listening) a talk related to the same topic of the reading. The first question's passage and talk will be about some aspect of campus life. The second question's passage and talk will be on an academic topic. The third format gives 20 seconds to prepare and 60 seconds to speak. For the first question, you will hear and watch a conversation between 2 speakers (2 students or a student and a faculty member). You will answer a question based on what you heard. For the second question, you will hear and watch an academic talk. Again, you will answer a question based on what you heard” (TestDEN©1997-2017).

4.2.3 HUFLIT's oral test structure

The traditional assessment method that has long been employed in the Foreign Language Department, HUFLIT embraces 4 crucial portions:

- a. group/pair forming
- b. topic selection
- c. role play
- d. scoring

In (a), a simple procedure that can be easily seen in any speaking courses not only in the English language, students are randomly formed in pairs by one of the two testers by matching them in the list.

In (b), also a simple and time-saving step, one representative of the group/pair is required to pick up one of the ready-made topics available in the school's website, most of which are relevant to what have been taught in the course to secure the motto “Test what we teach” (Stodola 1985).

In (c), before performing, the randomly selected pairs are offered about 5 minutes to review separately to avoid too-good co-operations with an expectation that test-takers will apply what they have learned in the course into a quasi-authentic environment. Then they are required to do a role-play, in which the take turn to ask and answer their partner's questions without any helps, any guidance, or any interruptions from the two examiners. This is the most crucial stage of the procedures that will be diligently analyzed in terms of validity, potentials, and flaws (Nguyen 2014).

In (d), basing on the scoring scheme in the figures, the two testers assess the testees' speaking traits: **fluency, intonation, pronunciation, proper use of vocabulary and structures** without interfering the discourse at any forms. The purpose is to construct a non-pressure situation in which the test-takers can feel free to express their ideas.

There is nothing to blame for when the test style, the two-scorer model, can apparently turn away some limitations frequently occurred in the oral tests, particularly in the status of minor institutions, of which personnel and governance are far from perfect. The students' answers confirm that Role play gives them too many opportunities leading to a dull motivation (Nguyen 2014).

Besides the above-mentioned advantages and disadvantages, the task also covers some shortcomings: (a) No retrospective reports, (b) no examiner's participation, (c) no scientific comparisons between tests in other institutions, (d) no feedback from peers, (e) no modifications for a long time, (f) no ways to help test takers to fully use their store of vocabulary and structures, (g) no clear-cut differences between level 3 and 4 though the topics may be changed, (h) questions from test takers are always in low level in terms of difficulty, validity, reliability (Nguyen 2014).

One of the most vital scientific criterions of the test is (a), which provides objective opinions from the test takers. Students after taking tests often complain only when they get low scores or failures and that the test composers never get any serious feedbacks from them is also a shortcoming.

(b) is viewed a good point in supplying a free authentic environment to examinees but it also hinders the scorers' important guidance in leading the task takers to the points required by their level.

(c) shows another scientific setback understood as a default. However, it can also be seen a lack of expertise. It's suggested that a good reference from international OPI be taken for selection and comparison.

(d) provides the scorers' constructive opinions for further improvements.

(e) can be set a huge hindrance. A modification stimulus should be implemented.

(f) unintentionally helps poor test takers maneuver the scoring procedures by employing lower-level vocabulary and structures. **In addition and more seriously, its washback effect may exacerbate the teaching and learning process in the institution** (Nguyen 2014).

(g) might leave some notion on students and they instinctively confront to tests in their own ways with a purpose quite different from earning speaking skill. That's also why learners cannot get high appreciation from employers as mentioned in the abstract (Nguyen 2014).

4.3 Differences between questions from well-trained testers and students

(h) shows the enormous drawback in testing. Students' questions are always simple with the purpose to help their partners and to get fluency, while the construct validity of any tests requests a diligent composition from test makers not from students. These questions absolutely cannot be viewed adequate in terms of construct validity, content validity, and reliability **for not scientifically constructed to exactly measure what the test needs as required by a norm.**

4.4 Preparation between OPI and HUFLIT's test

While in OPI, test takers have from 5-60 seconds for preparation, they have up to 5 minutes in Role play. Long allotted time reduces the validity due to problems around simultaneity.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of findings

Most respondents were not confident to agree that they can communicate with the native speaker of the target language with all topics after Speaking 4. Some were not sure they can.

Role play informs test topics long in advance while OPI and SOPI do not.

Role play let testees learn by heart ready-made questions and transitional sentences while OPI and SOPI do not.

Participants confirm that understanding questions from native speakers is more challenging.

They know for sure that international tests are in higher level in terms of testing varied targets and difficulty.

Almost half of the population said there should be an improvement in oral tests.

5.2 Conclusion

Role-play test style though has 25 years of existence, shows a lot of setbacks in terms of validity and reliability such as: test topics are publicized in advance, learners cocktail their own questions which cannot help measure crucial elements in proficiency, learning by heart questions and transitional sentences are allowed, long preparation before the test, testers usually do not get involved in the testing process. It is the right time, maybe a bit late, to improve the test based on the norms from OPI and SOPI like those of IELTS, TOEFL, TOEIC.

5.3 Recommendations

5.3.1 Fortest designers

The proposal is that each teacher in the faculty should provide 10 questions along with his frequent exam topic. These questions will be selected for use either by the authority or better by the examiners-in-charge to clearly measure the needed targets. To save real time in the testing room, only two or three questions should be employed. These questions should take high ratio, say 70%, in the scoring frame to ensure real ability from test takers is measured, not by ready-made conversations that have been learned by heart and help most examinees get hi-pass. In sum, to gain better evaluation on the task, there should be a more diligent investigation and a quantitative and qualitative research to provide a scientific comparison among various types or the same type but with different validity and reliability criteria. Modifications should soon be applied.

5.3.2 For students

Students should make efforts to practice spoken English whenever and wherever they have a chance. Free English speaking club is the best spot for both learning and entertainment. Always bear in mind that language proficiency is a huge weakness of Vietnamese job seekers.

5.3.3 For researchers

This is just a pilot study with a small number of respondents, unreliable as required in a real research. There is a need for further researching on whether or not Vietnamese teachers, or at least HUFLIT's lecturers, are willing to improve the test style to get closer to the international test criteria.

5.4 Limitations

Besides the above-mentioned limitations of a small sample, the new test may be hard to be applied in Vietnamese classrooms for its new and time-consuming properties. It is also difficult to persuade busy test designers to follow if they really do not want to have a change, especially in testing, a controversial section in VN's modern universities.

The findings in the pilot study may not gain the same results when being applied to a bigger population, in different classrooms, with different teachers, or in different institutions.

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